

**NEW SUBSPECIES OF *PURPURICENUS KAEHLERI*
(LINNAEUS, 1758) FROM CAUCASUS AND TRANSCAUCASIA
(COLEOPTERA, CERAMBYCIDAE)**

Maxim A. Lazarev*

* Free Economic Society of Russia, Department of Scientifics Conferences and All-Russian Projects, Tverskaya Str. 22a, Moscow 125009 RUSSIA. E-mail: cerambycidae@bk.ru; humanityspace@gmail.com; ORCID: 0000-0002-4040-0987

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ABSTRACT: *Purpuricenus kaehlerii miroshnikovi* Lazarev, ssp. n. is described from Russian North-West Caucasus and Western Georgia. The new taxon is characterized by usually rather red pronotum and peculiar genital structures.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, new subspecies

Up to now the species consisted of 8 subspecies (Danilevsky, 2021), including Eastern group of 2 subspecies: *Purpuricenus kaehlerii rossicus* Danilevsky, 2019 (described from Voronezh Region of Russia; figs. 6-7) and *P. k. menetriesi* Motschulsky, 1845 (described from Astrabad - now Gorgan in Iran). According to the generally accepted opinion (Danilevsky, 2019), *P. k. rossicus* is distributed along central and south parts of European Russia reaching northwards to the Moscow environs. It penetrates westwards to Germany and so includes territories of Ukraine, Moldavia, Belorussia, Czechia, Slovakia, Poland, Hungary, Romania, Austria, Bulgaria, Western Turkey. *P. k. menetriesi* was regarded to be distributed from Iran to Eastern Turkey and Transcaucasia with North Caucasus. Transitional populations between two subspecies in North Caucasus were not investigated, and south limits of *P. k. rossicus* area here were not clear.

Available material from Western Georgia and Nord-West Caucasus shows a big degree of morphological singularity. The specimens from here are not similar neither to eastern Caucasian (true *P. k. menetriesi*) specimens nor to *P. k. rossicus*. The new subspecies is described below.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M. L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia)

ML - collection of M. A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia)

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow University

Taxonomy

Purpuricenens kaehleri miroshnikovi Lazarev, ssp. n.

(Figs. 1-5, 8-9)

Purpuricenens kaehleri, Plavilstshikov, 1948: 117, part. - Whole Armenia (Central and South Europe, Caucasus, North Iran); Lobanov & al., 1982: 253; Miroshnikov, 1984: 7, part. - North-West Caucasus; 2012a: 140, part. - Middle and South Europe, Asia Minor, North Iran, Caucasus, South Urals; 2012b: 38; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 214, part. - "south of European part of USSR, Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia; West Europe, Turkey, North Iran; Sama, 2002: 54, part. - Europe, northern Turkey, Transcaucasia, northern Iran; Berger, 2012: 286, part. - "Europe centrale et méridionale, nord de la Turquie et de l'Iran, Transcaucasie".

Purpuricenens koehlerii Villiers, 1967: 363, part. - "Europe centrale et méridionale, Caucase, Arménie, Nord de l'Iran".

Purpuricenens budensis caucasicus, Sabbadini & Pesarini, 1992: 62 - "Armenia russa e turca".

Purpuricenens kaehlerii menetriesii, Danilevsky, 2007: 32, part. - "North Iran (Gorgan, Mazandaran, Zinzhan, Gilan), through Azerbaijan to Georgia, Dagestan republic of Russia and Krasnodar region and in north-east Turkey"; 2020: 76, 281 - "E: ST A: AB AR GG IN TR"; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2014: 158-159 (= *Purpuricenens budensis* var. *caucasicus* Th. Pic, 1902) - "Armenia, Helendorf (= Elenovka, now Sevan)" - a female, holotype of *P. budensis* var. *caucasicus* Th. Pic, 1902 was depicted and wrongly designated as a malelectotype.

Purpuricenens (s. str.) *kaehlerii menetriesii*, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 198, part. - "E: AB AR GG ST A: IN TR"; Miroshnikov, 2010: 248 - Adygeya; 2012b: 39, part. - Caucasus, North-East Anatolia, North Iran (Elburs).

Purpuricenens kaehlerii kaehlerii, Vartanis, 2018: 41, part. - Europe, northern Turkey, Transcaucasia.

Type locality. Russia, Krasnodar, Goryachiy Klyuch.

Description. The new taxon is much lighter than *P. k. menetriesii*, and characterized by very high level of individual variability; pronotum can never be totally black; the darkest specimen (a male from Mtskheta) has largely black pronotum with red spots at anterior angles; 3 males and one female have pronotum with black posterior dorsal half, but red laterally. Black pronotal area can be reduced to a pair of black spots or to small transverse bar. Sometimes only two small black spots at posterior angles are represented. Black spot can cover nearly whole elytral surface, touching scutellum; its lateral margin can be strait or curved; or elytral spot smaller, oval, or narrowly attenuated.

Parameres are moderately short and apex of penis is strongly sharpened.

Body length in males: 13.5-16.8 mm, body width: 4.4-5.7 mm; body length in females: 11.2-17.1 mm, body width: 3.8-5.7 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new taxon is close to *P. k. menetriesii* Motschulsky, 1845 (Figs. 10-11), and that's how it was determined before (Danilevsky, 2007; Miroshnikov, 2012b; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2014). It differs by high level of individual

variability and in general lighter color of pronotum and elytra; besides parameres in *P. k. menetriesi* are relatively shorter and penis with obliterated apex.

Figures 1-2. *Purpuricenus kaehlerii miroshnikovi* ssp. n.: 1. Holotype, male, Krasnodar, Goryachiy Klyuch, 30.6.1982, I. Berezhevskaya leg.; 2. Paratype, male, Mtskheta, 17.7.1915, Banjkovsky leg.

Figures 3-5. *P. k. miroshnikovi* ssp. n.: 3-4. Paratypes, females, Maykop, 12.7.1938; 5. Paratype, female, Svanetia, 23.7.1930.

Figures 6-11. Genitalia. *P. k. rossicus* Danilevsky, 2019: 6. apex of penis, Donensis province, Filonovskaya, 15.6.1912, A. Ilinsky; 7. parameres (same specimen); *P. k. miroshnikovi* ssp. n., paratype: 8. apex of penis, Anapa, Supsekh 2.7.1919 Zaitzev leg.; 9. parameres (same specimen). *P. k. menetriesi* Motschulsky, 1845: 10. apex of penis, Avrora (= Hirkan), 18.6.1980, M. Danilevsky leg.; 11. parameres (same specimen).

Type material. Holotype, male, Krasnodar, Goryachiy Klyuch, 30.6.1982, I. Berezhevskaya leg. - MD; 14 paratypes; 2 males, Anapa, Supsekh 2.7.1919 Zaitzev leg. - MD; 1 male, Abkhazia, Gagra - ML; 1 female, Abkhazia, Tsandripsh, 20.7.2008, G.B. Semishin leg. - MD; 2 males, Mtskhet, 17.7.1915, Banjkovsky leg. - MD; 1 female, Tiflis - ZMM; 1 female, Mtskhet, Didgora - ZMM; 1 female, Suram, 18.7.1919 - ZMM; 2 females, Maykop, 12.7.1938 - ZMM, 1 female, Maykop, 20.7.1937 - ZMM; 1 female, Maykop, 29.6.1939 - ZMM; 1 female, Svanetia, 23.7.1930 - ZMM.

Material used for comparison. *P. k. menetriesi*: 1 male, Azerbaijan, Masally District, *Fagus*, 27.7.1982 - ML; 2 males, 1 female, Azerbaijan, Avrora (Hirkan), *Paliurus spina-christi*, 18.6.1980, M. Danilevsky leg. - MD; 1 female, Talysh, Alekseevka, 25.6.1930, T. Safarov - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Iran, Gilan, 10 km E Tutkabon (E Rostam Abad) 350 m, 22.6.-2.7.2003, I. Rapuzzi leg. - MD.

Distribution. North Caucasus, Abkhazia, Georgia.

Remarks.

The label of the holotype of *P. budensis* var. *caucasicus* Th. Pic, 1902: "Caucasus / Helenendorf / Reitter" was wrongly interpreted by Rapuzzi & Sama (2014): as: "Armenia, Helendorf (= Elenovka, now Sevan)". In fact, it was Azerbaijan, Goygol (known as Helenendorf before 1931, Yelenino in 1931-1938, Khanlar in

1938-2008). So, *P. k. menetriesi* Motschulsky, 1845 = *P. budensis* var. *caucasicus* Th. Pic, 1902.

Purpuricenus caucasicus Th. Pic was wrongly accepted as a species by Miroschnikov (1984, 2010, 2012b), Danilevsky & Miroschnikov (1985) and Danilevsky (2010). According to Rapuzzi & Sama (2014), *Purpuricenus kaehleri* ssp. *menetriesi* Motschulsky, 1845 = *Purpuricenus budensis* v. *caucasicus* Th. Pic, 1902.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to well-known leader in the taxonomy of worldwide Cerambycidae fauna Major-general of the Forest Service Alexander Ivanovich Miroschnikov, who devotes his life to the study of Caucasian Cerambycidae. Miroschnikov (2012b: 41) underlined that the determination of Caucasian populations as *P. k. menetriesi* could be only conditionally accepted.

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